

Quinazolinyipyrazolines as Anti-inflammatory Agents

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RECENTLY, quinazolone nucleus has gained prominence due to its diverse biological activities¹. This prompted us to synthesise 2-[*o*-1'-acetyl-5'-(substituted-phenyl)-2-pyrazoline}-phenylaminomethyl]-3-(*o*-tolyl)-substituted-quinolin-4(3*H*)-ones (3a-1) from 2-[*o*-(substituted-cinnamoyl)phenylaminomethyl]-3-(*o*-tolyl)substituted-quinolin-4(3*H*)-ones (2a-1) by the reaction with hydrazine hydrate and glacial acetic acid. Compounds 2, in turn, have been synthesised by refluxing 2-[*o*-(acetyl)phenylaminomethyl]-3-(*o*-tolyl)substituted-quinazolin-4-(3*H*)-ones (1a, b) with different arylaldehydes in absolute ethanol (Scheme 1). These compounds when evaluated for anti-inflammatory activity in albino rats at an oral dose of 50 mg/kg showed varying degree of protection (7.2–34.0%) against carrageenin induced oedema.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was confirmed by tlc using silica gel G. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃/DMSO-d₆) on a Varian A 90 D instrument using TMS as internal standard.

2-[*o*-(Acetyl)phenylaminomethyl]-3-(*o*-tolyl)quinolin-4-(3*H*)-one (1a): To a mixture of 2-bromoethyl-3-(*o*-tolyl)quinolin-4-(3*H*)-one (0.01 mol) and 2-aminoacetophenone (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was added a few drops of pyridine and the solution refluxed for 8–10 h. It was then poured on crushed ice containing a few drops of hydrochloric acid. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol, to give the product: 1a (60%), m.p. 213° (Found: C, 75.26; H, 5.52; N, 11.01. C₂₄H₂₁N₃O₂ requires: C, 75.16; H, 5.48; N, 10.96%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 250 (NH) and 1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 6.65–8.05 (12H, m, ArH), 3.37 (3H, s, OCH₃Ar), 3.60 (3H, s, COCH₃), 4.45 (1H, bs, NH), 3.60 (2H, d, CH₂NH); 1b (X=6-Br) m.p. 276° (Found: C, 62.12; H, 4.39; N, 10.03. C₂₄H₂₀N₃O₂Br requires: C, 62.35; H, 4.32; N, 9.09%).

2-[*o*-(Substituted-cinnamoyl)phenylaminomethyl]-3-(*o*-tolyl)substituted-quinolin-4-(3*H*)-one (2b): Compound 1b (0.02 mol) was refluxed with *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.02 mol) in absolute ethanol having

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	X	R	Mol. formula	M p. °C	Anti-inflam. activity (%)
1a	H		C ₂₄ H ₃₁ N ₅ O ₃	213	8.6
1b	B ₁		C ₂₄ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃ Br	276	10.3
2a	H	2-F	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₅ O ₃ F	186	9.6
2b	H	2-OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ N ₅ O ₄	197	11.1
2c	H	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ N ₅ O ₄	136	25.2
2d	H	4-N-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂₃ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₃	157	—
2e	H	2-Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₅ O ₃ Cl	171	20.6
2f	H	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₅ O ₃	126	—
2g	6-Br	2-F	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₃ BrF	169	11.7
2h	6-B ₁	2-OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₅ O ₄ Br	189	30.1
2i	6-Br	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₅ O ₄ Br	201	—
2j	6-Br	4-N-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ N ₄ O ₃ Br	271	7.2
2k	6-Br	2-Cl	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₃ ClBr	203	21.4
2l	6-Br	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₅ O ₃ Br	263	—
3a	H	2-F	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ N ₅ O ₃ F	211	10.5
3b	H	2-OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₃₁ N ₅ O ₄	219	28.1
3c	H	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₃₁ N ₅ O ₄	198	11.5
3d	H	2-Cl	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₅ O ₃ Cl	181	29.4
3e	H	4-N-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂₃ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₃	236	12.3
3f	H	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₃	156	12.8
3g	6-Br	2-F	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ N ₅ O ₃ BrF	191	21.2
3h	6-Br	2-OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₅ O ₄ Br	256	34.0
3i	6-Br	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₅ O ₄ Br	286	11.7
3j	6-Br	2-Cl	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ N ₅ O ₃ BrCl	293	13.4
3k	6-Br	4-N-(CH ₃) ₂	C ₂₃ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₃ Br	277	19.3
3l	6-Br	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₅ O ₃ Br	296	16.6

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses

a few drops of glacial acetic acid for 12 h. The mixture was washed with diethyl ether and the resulting solid recrystallised from DMF-petroleum ether, (67%), m.p. 197° (Found: C, 74.31; H, 5.49; N, 8.51. C₂₃H₂₇N₅O₄ requires: C, 74.27; H, 5.22; N, 8.12%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 300 (NH), 1 720 (C=O), 1 610 (CH=CH) and 1 590 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 7.70–8.50 (16H, m, ArH), 8.6 (1H d, =CHAr), 6.75 (1H, d, COCH=), 3.40 (6H, s, 2 × OCH₃Ar), 4.75 (1H, ss, NH) and 3.55 (2H, d, CH₂NH). Other compounds (Table 1) were prepared (55–70%) similarly.

2-[o-(1'-Acetyl-5'-(substituted-phenyl)-2-pyrazoline)phenylaminomethyl]-3-(o-tolyl)substituted-quinolin-4-(3H)-one (3b): To a solution of 2b (0.02 mol), hydrazine hydrate (98%) in DMF and a few drops of glacial acetic acid were added and stirred for 48 h. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 6 h, cooled and poured into ice-water. The resulting solid was recrystallised from benzene, (56%), m.p. 219° (Found: C, 73.72; H, 5.51; N, 12.41. C₃₄H₃₁N₅O₄ requires: C, 73.24; H, 5.56; N, 12.56%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 300 (NH) and 1 520 (N–N); δ (DMSO-d₆) 7.65–8.80 (16H, m, ArH), 3.40 (6H, s, 2 × OCH₃Ar), 4.50 (1H, bs, NH), 3.65 (2H, d, CH₂NH), 5.50 (1H, t, CHAr), 4.75 (2H, d, CH₂ of pyrazoline ring) and 3.50 (3H, s, COCH₃). Similarly other compounds (Table 1) were synthesised (55–65%).

Anti-inflammatory activity: All the compounds were tested for their anti-inflammatory activity following the method of Winter *et al.*² The mean increase in paw volume due to carrageenin induced

oedema was measured according to the micropipette method.³ The results are recorded in Table 1.

In view of limited structural variants, it is difficult to establish a clear cut SAR. In case of compounds 1 and 2 (30.1%) activity was exhibited by compound 2h. In case of compounds 3, cyclisation of substituted-cinnamoyl moiety (chalcone) into pyrazoline ring results, in general, greater anti-inflammatory activity. However, the presence of 2-OCH₃(R) caused maximum protection in carrageenin induced oedema as shown by anti-inflammatory activity of 2h (30.1%) and 3h (34.0%).

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